

Sufi Influence on Baul Philosophy and Music : A Historical Analysis

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Abstract

Sufism emerged in Arabia around the time of Islam's advent. Though it originated in Arabia, it flourished and developed in Persia before spreading to various parts of the world. Iranian Pirwad (the tradition of spiritual masters) became quite popular in India. The primary reason for its popularity lies in the contribution of Indian Brahminism, since the philosophical foundations of Brahminism and Sufism are largely identical. Alongside northern India, after Islam entered Bengal, it drew somewhat closer to the Upanishadic Hindu-Buddhist spiritual traditions of this region — traditions that were themselves adjacent to the Sufi path of Islamic mysticism. When the common people of Bengal converted to Islam from Hinduism and Buddhism, they carried into the new faith many ideas, concepts, and beliefs from their former religions. As a result, the spiritual practices of the lower classes of Bengal became syncretic in character. This is why the influence of various religious philosophies can be observed among Bengal's spiritual practitioners.

In time, this mixed tradition gave rise to various sub-sects — among them emerged, particularly in Rarh Bengal, a folk-religious sub-sect known as the Bauls. The influence of Sufism can be observed among Lalon Fakir and the Baul-Fakirs of Bengal, visible in their philosophy, music, thought, and everyday life. Ordinary people do not distinguish between a Guru (Hindu saint) and a Sufi Pir-Fakir. These Bauls, as well as Pir-Fakirs, considered themselves Sufis — even though many non-Islamic elements were embedded in their practices. In our country, Baul-Fakiri songs are most prevalent in Rarh Bengal. The Bauls possess no institutionalised philosophy or scripture; through song, they seek the object of their worship. In their own terminology, they call this 'Moner Manush' (the Man of the Heart), 'Achin Pakhi' (the Unknown Bird), 'Mon Monuyar', 'Adhara' (the Unattainable), and 'Atal' (the Unfathomable). Their deity dwells within the living body. To know the microcosm of the body is to know the macrocosm of Brahman — this is their religio-philosophy.

The Vedic dictum 'Atmanam Viddhi' and the Sufi axiom 'Man Arafah Nafsahu, Faqad Arafah Rabbahu' — 'To know oneself is to know God' — are both principles that Baul philosophy follows. The Bauls do not discriminate on the basis of caste — they do not recognise Hindu-Muslim caste distinctions, high-low social hierarchies, or rich-poor class divisions. Although both Hindu and Muslim scriptural religions and social norms maintain various forms of such discrimination, Islam, despite carrying the ideals of equality and brotherhood in principle, has not always upheld these in practice. Lalon Shah and other Baul masters broke the rigid rule-bound strictures of scriptural or Sharia-bound religion and created a liberating humanitarianism and a path of mysticism marked by simplicity. Lalon conducted his sadhana (spiritual practice) at his ashram in Chheuria, Kushtia. People from peasant and weaver communities took initiation in the Baul tradition. Lalon had hundreds of thousands of Baul disciples. Bauls are primarily wandering mystics; apart from farming and weaving as normal occupations, some also practised mendicancy.

The Baul tradition includes the practice of deha-sadhana (body-centred spiritual discipline). In later periods, because of certain tantric and tamasic (dull, hedonistic) practices, the conservative society did not look favourably upon the Bauls; Sharia-observant Muslims did not easily accept this tradition. They would issue fatwas against the Bauls. Though opposition and attempts to uproot them were made, their contribution in the domain of religious and social reconciliation is nonetheless significant.

Keywords

Sufi, Auliya, Pir, Akhara, Shariat, Haqiqat, Sain, Zikir, Daemi, Barkhoja.

Introduction

From childhood, I had seen Bauls in many places and listened to their songs. The worldwide respect accorded to Bauls was not something I had fully understood then. There are Baul akharas (ashrams/lodges) in various locations. 'Baul' is the name of a spiritual sub-sect of Bengal. Though Bauls are scattered all across Bengal, they are particularly popular in Nadia, Murshidabad, Birbhum, Bankura, and 24 Parganas in West Bengal, and in Kushtia, Chuadanga, Meherpur, Jhenaidah, Pabna, Faridpur, and Jessore districts of East Bengal. The Kushtia sub-division of undivided Nadia was the spiritual heartland of the Baul community. In the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, a group of devotees — believers in the love of God from all religions, both Hindu and Muslim — became known in Bengal as Bauls.

Objective of study

The present study aims to examine the historical and philosophical connections between Sufism and the Baul tradition of Bengal. It seeks to trace the origins and development of the Baul sect and analyse how Sufi thought influenced its philosophy, music, and spiritual practice. The study also attempts to identify the shared principles between Sufi and Baul sadhana, particularly in relation to the Guru-disciple tradition, rejection of caste discrimination, and body-centred spirituality. Furthermore, it aims to explore the role of key figures such as Siraj Sain and Lalon Fakir in shaping the syncretic character of the Baul tradition. Finally, the study seeks to establish that the Baul tradition of Bengal is a product of the historical convergence of Hindu, Buddhist, and Islamic mystical streams, with Sufism playing a central and defining role.

Review of Literature

Upendranath Bhattacharya's *Banglar Baul O Baul Gaan* (1964) remains the most comprehensive study of the Baul tradition, tracing its origins and philosophical framework in detail. Ahmad Sharif's *Baul Tattwa* (2014) argues that the shared Buddhist heritage of lapsed Buddhists enabled the Baul tradition to develop as a confluence of Hindu and Muslim spiritual streams. Kshitimohan Sen Shastri's *Banglar Baul* (1993) documented the egalitarian social character of the Baul community and its common opposition to caste discrimination with Sufism. Muhammad Enamul Haq's *Bange Sufi Prabhav* (2021) examined how Sufi philosophy gradually merged with local Hindu-Buddhist traditions of Bengal, giving rise to a syncretic devotional culture. Abdul Wahab's *Banglar Baul Sufi Sadhana O Sangit* (1999) directly analysed the relationship between Baul and Sufi sadhana and music. Md. Abdul Karim Mia's *Lalon Darshaner Bhumika* (2021) provided a detailed philosophical analysis of Lalon Fakir's thought in relation to both Sufi and Vaishnava traditions. Reynold A. Nicholson's *The Mystics of Islam* (1914) offered the classical framework for understanding Sufi mysticism, which finds direct parallels in Baul body-philosophy. Despite this rich scholarship, a focused comparative analysis of the philosophical and musical parallels between Sufism and the Baul tradition remains limited, and the present study seeks to address this gap.

Main Text**Origins of the Baul Tradition**

Describing the origin and development of Baul sadhana, Dr. Upendranath Bhattacharya states that Aul Chand and his disciple Madhab Bibi, following the Maithunic (tantric-sexual) methods of Chaitanya Deva's sadhana, inaugurated the Baul sect, and it was through the efforts of Madhab Bibi's disciple, Birbhadra, that this movement spread. Support for this view can be found in the following song, in which Nityananda says to his son Birbhadra:

Shighra kari jao tumi Madina shahare--- [Go swiftly to the city of Madina---]

Tatha jai shiksha laha Madhab bibir sane, [Go there and take instruction from Madhab Bibi,]

Tahar sharire Prabhu achen bartamane. [For within her body the Lord presently dwells.]

Madhab bibi bine tohar shiksha dite nai, [Without Madhab Bibi, there is none to teach you,]

Tanhar sharire achen Chaitanya Gossai. [For in her body abides Chaitanya Gossai.]

Regarding the origin and development of the Baul tradition, Dr. Ahmad Sharif states: 'Those lapsed Buddhists who accepted Islam, and those lapsed Buddhists who became absorbed into Hindu society yet continued the religious practices of their ancestors, were the ones who later became affiliated with the Baul sect. It was because of this shared Buddhist heritage that the Baul tradition could develop through the confluence of Hindus and Muslims.'

The word 'Baul' first appears in the sixteenth-century Vaishnava philosophical text *Chaitanyacharitamrita*, composed by Krishnadas Kaviraj. The word 'Aul' also appears alongside it in this work, as in the verse:

Ami ta Baul, alga kahite alga kahi. [I am but a Baul; I keep saying what is loosened.]

Krishner madhurya-shtrote ami jai bahi. [I am carried along in the current of Krishna's sweetness.]

It is further noted in the same text:

Baulike kahiya loke haila aul. [By calling him a Baul, people took him for a madman (Aul).]

Baulike kahiya hate na bikay chaul. [By calling him a Baul, rice cannot be sold in the market.]

Baulike kahiya kaje nahika aul. [By calling him a Baul, no confusion arises in the work.]

Baulike kahiya iha kahiyaache Baul. [By calling him a Baul, this is what a Baul has said.]

Etymology of the Word 'Baul'

In the sixteenth century, the word 'Baul' can also be found used in Daulat Uzir Bahram Khan's narrative poem 'Laila-Majnu.' In Sanskrit, 'Bakul' or 'Batul' is believed by some researchers to be the origin of the word 'Baul'. According to Prakrit grammar, the consonant 't' between two vowels ('a' and 'u') is elided — and it is precisely through this rule that 'Batul' became 'Baul'. The meaning of 'Batul' is mad, eccentric, or crazed. Thus 'Baul' means 'one who is mad for outward spiritual truth.'

The word 'Baul' may also have originated from the Arabic 'Aul', where the companion prefix 'Ba' gives the compound term its sense. 'Aul' means a practitioner of the simple path. These practitioners are also known as 'Aul' or 'Darvesh'. In the Sufi tradition there is a group of practitioners called 'Ba-Al'. Many scholars think the word 'Baul' may also have derived from here. In Arabic, 'Ba' means soul and 'Al' or 'ul' means seeker — thus 'Baul' means 'seeker of the soul'. Some scholars believe 'Baul' derived from 'Bakul' — meaning one who is eager to find the 'Man of the Heart' (the inner divine). Others have suggested the Sanskrit 'Vayu' (wind/breath) as the root — those who seek spiritual power through breathing exercises are called Baul. Still others derive it from 'Baur' or 'Baura', meaning madman. Dr. Suniti Kumar Chattopadhyay has noted that the word is linguistically derived — it evolved from 'Baula' to 'Baula' and finally to 'Baul'.

Whether 'Baul' derives from the Sanskrit 'Bakul' or 'Batul', or from the Arabic 'Aul' or Hindi 'Baul', the meaning ultimately becomes either 'mad with love for God' or 'devoted servant of God'. The dictionary definition of 'Baul' is: a distinctive sect of practitioners who are liberated from religious narrowness and conditioning.

Philosophy and Practice of Baul Sadhana

A clear resemblance can be seen between Baul sadhana, which is centred on the body, and ancient Indian Samkhya, Yoga, and Tantra. However, Baul sadhana is fundamentally opposed to Vedic or Brahminical practices and is inclined towards Maithunic (tantric-sexual) methods. Bauls did not accept the distinction between Hindu and Muslim. There was no caste discrimination in the Baul's religion and conduct. They did not give importance to either the Quran or the Puranas as scriptures. They could love people regardless of caste, religion, or class. Lalou believed that humans are supreme.

Though there was no division among themselves, they were divided into two sub-communities: 1) Hindu Sahajiya Bauls, and 2) Sufi Muslim Fakir Bauls or Auliya. Despite this classification, Hindu Bauls on one hand used the terminology of Sufi sadhana, while Sufi Bauls on the other hand practised Yoga-Tantra. In Baul sadhana, neither injured the other. The core principle of Baul sadhana — love for all people regardless of caste, religion, or class — touched both Hindus and Muslims equally. The primary goal of their practice was to transcend individual identity and love humanity. They believed that by renouncing ego and worldly existence (fana), union with God (baqa) can be attained.

Since Baul sadhana has been influenced by many religious traditions, Baul songs under Hindu influence employ figures such as Radha-Krishna, Shiva-Shivani, Maya-Brahma, and Vishnu-Lakshmi as symbols of the masculine-feminine principle; under Muslim influence, terms such as Maqam, Manzil, Latifa, Sirajunnira, Allah, Qadir, Ghani, Rasul, Ruh, Anal Haq, Adam-Hawa, Muhammad-Khadija, and Ali-Fatema appear as symbolic metaphors. These are further combined with Buddhist Nath, Niranjana, mythological analogies, and many sayings from the Quran and Hadith.

According to their method of sadhana, Bauls had two stages: 1) Pritha (practice with a consort) and 2) Tatha (practice without a consort). At the Pritha stage, various tantric rituals were performed with a female companion (sadhini). These were called Baddha Bauls (bound Bauls). Those who followed the Tatha path had no companion and were free-form mystical practitioners. Dr. Aditya Mukhopadhyay, in his book *Banglar Baul*, has divided Bauls into three classes:

1. The first class are the Dharmatantric Bauls. They strictly observe the rules of sadhana, live in ashrams or akharas, keep seva-dasis (ritual female attendants), travel to different places, and consider the Guru to be the supreme object of worship.
2. The second class are the householder Bauls. They take initiation from a Guru and practise sadhana according to their capacity.
3. The third class are those who learn songs from a Guru but do not observe the rules. They live as they please and sing Baul songs when the opportunity arises.

Today, however, there has emerged a class of 'fake Bauls' or 'pretender Bauls' who wear saffron-coloured robes and sing Baul songs in fairs, fields, and on trains and buses — with earning money through song being their sole purpose. Additionally, we can identify a class called 'shaukhin Bauls' (Bauls by fancy) — for instance, Rabindranath Tagore was a shaukhin Baul: he loved to think of himself as a Baul in temperament, dress, and demeanour.

The Eighteenth and Nineteenth Centuries

In the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, this mystical sect spread notably across Bengal. Among them, the Guru-disciple lineage, Maithuna (tantric-sexual union), and the doctrine of the self (atma-tattwa) were all of equal importance. In Baul sadhana, the Guru-principle is supreme — the central purpose of this tradition is to maintain the Guru-disciple lineage. They believed that without initiation from a Guru, one cannot attain spiritual realisation. In the tantric doctrine of Maithuna, during the raising of Kundalini energy, the Ganga (Ida) and Yamuna (Pingala) channels must be made to meet at the Saraswati (Sushumna) — a confluence called Triveni Sangam. Thereafter, when the divine drop falls upon the thousand-petalled lotus (Sahasrara) situated at the crown of the head, the state of Mahabhava or Sahaja arises. Atma-tattwa is the endeavour to realise the formless, blissful self within the formed body. To immerse oneself in the ocean of form for the sake of the formless — and from that natural disposition to ascend into higher states of being — this is Atma-tattwa.

Siraj Sain : The Eighteenth-Century Baul Master

Siraj Sain (1718–1798) was a Baul practitioner and philosopher of the eighteenth century. He composed numerous Baul songs. Syed Zahid Hasan compiled and documented over a hundred of his songs in the book *Lalon Guru Siraj Saier Gaan*. Siraj Sain was Lalon Fakir's initiating Guru. He was the ninth-generation spiritual disciple of Nizamuddin Auliya. One of his songs is given below:

Apnar apni phana hole se bhed jana jabe. [When the self dissolves into itself, that mystery shall be known.]

Kona name dakile tare hridakashe uday habe. [By whatever name you call upon Him, He shall rise in the sky of the heart.]

Arabi te bale Allah, pharasit koy Khodatale, [In Arabic He is called Allah; in Persian, Khodatale;]

God bolecha Yishurchela bhinna deshe bhinna bhabe. ['God' say Christ's disciples — in different lands, in different ways.]

Moner bhab prakashite bhashar uday e jagate, [To express the feeling of the heart, language arose in this world;]

Manatit adhar chinte bhashabak nahi pabe. [To know the Unattainable beyond the mind, language and speech cannot reach.]

Allah hari bhajan pujan e sakal manusher srijan, [Allah, Hari — devotion and worship, all are creation of human beings;]

Anamak chenay bechan bagindiya na sambhabe. [Recognition of the Nameless through words — this is not possible in language.]

Apanate apni phana hole tare jabe jana, [Only when the self is dissolved within itself shall He be known;]

Siraj Saim koy Lalon kana swaruper rup dekh sankshhepe. [Says Siraj Sain: O Lalon, blind one — see the form of the Formless in brief.]

Lalon Fakir: The Supreme Baul Master

The greatest Baul practitioner and lyricist of all times is Lalon Fakir. He is said to have been born in 1772 CE (or alternatively 1775 CE) in a Hindu family in Bhandra village of Kushtia. He despised religious fanaticism. Though Lalon never spoke of his own personal life, he was at once a Baul practitioner, philosopher, lyricist, composer, and singer. The principles (tattvas) visible in his songs are: Guru-tattwa (the principle of the Guru), Nabi-tattwa (the principle of the Prophet), Atma-tattwa (the principle of the self), Krishna-tattwa, Bhakti-tattwa (devotion), Prema-tattwa (love), Parama-tattwa (the Supreme), and Sadhana-tattwa (the principle of spiritual practice). The distinctive features of Lalon Fakir's songs are: 1) Body-philosophy and humanism, 2) Religious liberalism, 3) Love-sadhana or devotion, and 4) Simple and direct mode of expression.

Lalon was a humanist Baul practitioner. The non-sectarian Lalon Shah, through his songs and words, even influenced Rabindranath Tagore. He placed humanity above all distinctions of religion, class, and caste. He expressed this in his song:

Shab loke koy Lalon ki jat sansare. [Everyone asks: O Lalon, what caste are you in this world?]

Lalon bole jater ki rup dekhilam na ei najare. [Lalon says: I could not see the form of caste with my eyes.]

Keu mala keu tasbi galay, taite ye jat bhinna balay, [Some wear a garland, some a rosary — and by this they claim to be of different castes;]

Jaoa kingba asar belay, jater ching ray kar re. [But at the time of coming or going, whose mark of caste remains?]

Jadi sunnat dile hoy Musalman, narir tabe ki hoy bidhan, [If circumcision makes a man a Muslim, what then is ordained for women?]

Baman chini paita praman, bamani chini kemane re. [A Brahmin I recognise by the sacred thread — how then do I recognise a Brahmin woman?]

Jagat bere jeter katha loke gaurab kare jatha tatha, [The world extols the matter of caste — people boast of it everywhere;]

Lalon se koy jeter phata ghuchiyache sadh-bajare. [Lalon says: the veil of caste has been lifted in the marketplace of spiritual seekers.]

His ashram was at Sheulia (or Chheuria) in Kumarkhali, Kushtia. Though he had few disciples in the beginning, he later had nearly ten thousand disciples, it is said. They addressed him as 'Sain' (Lord). He taught his disciples ethics and spirituality. In his own words: 'Ja ache bhande, tai ache brahmande' — 'What is in the body, that is in the universe.' The core principle of Lalon's Baul sadhana was a body-centred spiritual practice synthesised from Vaishnava Sahajiya, Buddhist Sahajiya, and Sufism. Lalon Fakir believed that within every human being dwells the 'Moner Manush' (Man of the Heart) — God. And that 'Man of the Heart' can be found through self-sadhana. Within the body resides the 'Moner Manush' or the 'Achin Pakhi' (Unknown Bird). On this subject he composed his famous song:

Khachara bhitara achin pakhi kemane ashe jay. [How does the unknown bird come and go within the cage?]

Dharte parle mon-beri ditam tahar pay. [Could I catch it, I would put mind-fetters on its feet.]

Ath-kuthuri noy daraja-ata, majhe majhe jhalka-kata, [Eight chambers with nine locked doors, with occasional flashes in between;]

Tar upar ache sadar-kotha — ayna-mahal tay. [And above them is the upper room — the palace of mirrors.]

Mon, tui roili khachara ashe, khaca je toar toiri kaca banshi, [O mind, you linger around the cage — the cage is made of green bamboo;]

Kontin khaca parbe khashe, Lalon koy, khaca khule, [One day the cage will fall apart, says Lalon, opening the cage —]

Se pakhi kotha khane palay. [Where does that bird then fly?]

The Baul practitioner envisioned a future society free from exploitation and inequality. Expressing the yearning for such a society, Lalon Fakir sang:

Emon samaj kabe go srijan habe, [When, O when, will such a society be created,]

Jedin Hindu-Musalman Baudhdha Khrishtan jati-gotra nahi rabe. [When the distinctions of Hindu, Muslim, Buddhist, Christian — of caste and clan — shall exist no more?]

Shonaye lober buli, nebe na keu kandher jhuli, [No one shall be lured by greed, no one shall carry another's burden on their shoulder;]

Itar atrap bali dure thele nahi debe. [No one shall be pushed away with the taunt of 'lowborn' or 'outcaste'.]

Amir fakir hoye ekthain, sabar paona pabe sabai, [The wealthy and the poor shall stand together in one place, each receiving their due;]

Ashraf baliya rehai bhebe kehoi nahi pabe. [No one shall escape by claiming the privilege of being 'ashraf' (noble-born).]

Dharmakul gotra jatir, tulbe na go keha jigir, [No one shall invoke the matter of religious family, clan, or caste;]

Kende bole Lalon Fakir ke ba dekhay debe. [Weeping, Lalon Fakir asks: who will show us that world?]

However, many scholars have claimed that this particular song was not composed by Lalon Fakir himself — there is a touch of modernity in its language and sentiment. Even so, one can say that if some other person composed it, they expressed therein their personal or collective aspiration. Dr. Girindranath Das, in his book *Banger Pir Piranider Katha*, evaluating Lalon Shah, writes: 'Lalon Shah did not use physical force — sword or any other weapon — against conservatives of both Hindu and Muslim communities. He was a tantric poet, a connoisseur, who relished the flavour of life, — and the soil of nineteenth-century Bengali literature.'

Lalon Fakir — supreme practitioner of humanism, religious liberalism, love-sadhana, and pure devotion — passed away on the 17th of October, 1890, at the age of 116. After his death, the journal *Hitakari* honoured him with the title 'Mahatma'. Among his distinguished disciples were Dudu Shah, Panju Shah, Gagan Harkara, Hasan Raja, Gopal Gossai, Madan Baul, Gopal, and Haore Gossai.

The Relationship Between Sufism and the Baul Tradition

The Sufis and Bauls share a close relationship. Both traditions have grown around a broad humanity. They have placed human religion and human love upon the highest seat. Both have given primacy to love and harmony in their sadhana and songs. They discuss the presence of the Supreme Spirit or soul within the body. Just as the Sufi concept of the devotional impulse or love leads towards union with Allah, so too Bauls spend their entire lives in search of the 'Moner Manush' (Man of the Heart). Therefore, the sadhana of both traditions is centred on self-realisation. Both the Baul and the Sufi are believers and free thinkers. They have not looked upon people differently on the basis of religion. Both have opposed conventional, customary religious practice by renouncing external rituals.

A similarity can also be observed in external dress. Like the Sufis, Bauls wear the alkhalla (long robe) with patches of torn cloth. Many Bauls are seen wearing the alkhalla alongside a tilak (forehead mark) and kanthi (necklace-beads) — a synthesis of Sufi influence alongside Vaishnava influence. The practice of wearing a 'khilka' (from the Arabic word for a sleeveless long coat) among Bauls finds its parallel in the garments of Sufi practitioners.

The Guru Principle in Both Traditions

Both Sufi and Baul traditions are grounded in the Guru-principle. In Sufi sadhana, the Murshid (Guru) leads the Murid (disciple) from darkness to light. The Guru shows the disciple the right

path. The Guru alone is the ultimate truth for the disciple. By earning the Guru's trust, the disciple attains the compassionate Allah. Bauls hold the same conviction. Therefore Lalon sings:

Murshid bine ki dhan ar ache re mon e jagate, [Is there any wealth other than the Murshid in this world, O heart?]

Je nam smarane here, tapita anta shital kare, [By whose name remembered, the burning within is cooled,]

Bhabandhan jwala jay go dure japa oi nam dibarate. [And the pain of worldly bondage goes away — chant that name day and night.]

Murshider charaner sudha, pan karile jabe khuda, [The nectar of the Murshid's feet — drink it and hunger shall go;]

Kara nare dele dwidha, sehi Murshid sehi Khoda. [Have no hesitation in your heart — that Murshid is that God himself.]

Nirakare hakim Niranjan Murshid-rup oi bhajan pathe. [The Formless sovereign, the Pure One — in the form of the Murshid, on the path of devotion.]

Equality and Freedom from Caste

Like Sufi practitioners, the Baul community supports a liberal outlook. Both are opposed to the system of caste discrimination. Like the Sufi masters, Bauls protect the dignity of human beings without regard to religion — they have transcended the notion of superiority and inferiority and accorded dignity to all people. Therefore, in Lalon's song we find:

Manushtattwa jar satya hoy mone, [One for whom the tattwa (principle) of humanity is genuine in the heart —]

Se ki anya tattwa mane. [Can such a one follow any other tattwa?]

Matir dhibi kathera chabi, bhut bhabishat ar debaDebi, [Mounds of earth, wooden idols, past and future, gods and goddesses —]

Bhole na se esab rupi, manush bhaje dibanishine. [Such a person is not deceived by these forms, but worships humanity day and night.]

The Four Paths of Sufi Sadhana

Sufi sadhana has various paths: Shariat (religious law), Tariqat (the mystical path), Haqiqat (truth), and Ma'rifat (gnosis). To succeed in these four paths of sadhana, the practitioner must become 'Zinda Mara' — 'dead before death'. Lalon Fakir speaks of the sadhana of these four paths:

Satya je shariat, hak balo sei haqiqate, [That which is true is Shariat; call that the truth in Haqiqat;]

Tariqate koy sadhana, marefate ebadat kara, haite habe jinde mara. [Tariqat speaks of sadhana; in Ma'rifat, worship — and one must die while still alive.]

Barzakh Sadhana and Zikir

The culmination of Sufi sadhana is the contemplation or zikir (remembrance) of the Murshid's form in the mind's eye — this is called 'Barzakh' sadhana. Through Barzakh, one attains Allah. Barzakh holds an immense significance in Sufi practice. Since it is difficult to keep the mind focused on formless sadhana, zikir is recommended while remembering the form of the Murshid. Without Barzakh sadhana, the 'Adhar Manush' (the Unattainable Person) cannot be found. Lalon Fakir says on this:

Nam sadhan biphala barjokh bine, [The practice of the Name is futile without Barzakh;]

Ekhane shekhane barzokh mul thikana, tai dekh mone mone. [Here and there, Barzakh is the ultimate abode — see this in the depth of your mind.]

Jemon nauka thik noy bine daray, [Just as a boat cannot be steadied without an oar,]

*Ni-akare mon ki daray, Lalon miche ghure beray, [Can the mind remain steady in the formless?
Lalon wanders in vain,]*

Adhar dharte chay barzokh bine. [Wanting to grasp the Unattainable without Barzakh.]

Harmony, Peace, and Ecumenism

Like Sufis, peace, friendship, love, and religious neutrality are among the essential virtues of the Bauls. Therefore they say:

Kali Krishna God Khoda, kona name nahi badha, mon Kali Krishna God Khoda bala re. [Kali, Krishna, God, Khoda (Allah) — no name is forbidden; O heart, say Kali, Krishna, God, Khoda.]

Bringing in this context, Abdul Wahab says: 'Even among political architects, the shadow of the Sufi-Vaishnava Baul liberal humanist consciousness had fallen. Therefore, it can be said that the influence of Sufi and Baul sadhana on our life and literature is far-reaching.' Kshitimohan Sen Shastri believes that in both communities, there is no distinction of Hindu-Muslim or high-low. He notes that Baul Monai's disciple was Kalchand Mistry, whose disciple was Harai Namasudra, whose disciple was Dinu (a member of the Nat caste), and so on — a lineage that traverses caste boundaries entirely.

Zikir: The Practice of Divine Remembrance

One aspect of Sufi sadhana is Zikir (remembrance/chanting of the divine name). Sufis believe that through Zikir, Allah can be attained. The primary Zikir is 'La ilaha illallah' — 'There is no deity worthy of worship except Allah.' Like the Sufis, Lalon Fakir declares:

Mukhe paro sada La ilaha illal la ei ain bhejilen Rasulallah. [Always recite with your mouth: La ilaha illal la — this law was revealed by the Rasul of Allah.]

At the same time, Sufis believe that no one should be equated with Allah — Allah has no partner (sharik). When Zikir is performed without attributing a partner to Allah, one attains Him. Similarly, Lalon Fakir suggests:

La sharik janiye take, karo jeker del mukhe, [Knowing Him as without partner (La Sharik), do Zikir with a sincere heart and mouth;]

Mukti pabi thakbi shukhe, dekhbi re nur Bazlullah. [You shall find liberation and live in happiness, and behold the light of Bazlullah.]

Daemi Namaz: The Perpetual Prayer

In Islam, the prescribed prayer according to Sharia is called Qa'imi Namaz. In Sufi practice, there is a prayer called Daemi Namaz. This prayer has no fixed time — it is perpetual; even in the state of sleep, by performing Daemi Namaz, one can attain the vision of Allah. Lalon Fakir's songs also mention this:

Para re dayemi namaz, e din hala akhir, [Read the Daemi Namaz — this day has come to its end;]

Mashuk rup rekhe dele, dekh ashak bati thele, [Keeping the form of the Beloved within your heart, see — the lover's lamp is lit;]

Kiba shakal ki baikale, dayemir nai abadhari. [Whether morning or evening, the Daemi (prayer) has no fixed time.]

The Five Maqams

For attaining the nearness or proximity of Allah, the Sufis speak of five maqams (spiritual stations): Nasut, Malakut, Jabarut, Lahut, and Hahut. Similarly, Baul songs also reference these five maqams:

Dekhbi jadi sahaj manush ruper ghare jao, [If you wish to see the simple human, go to the home of forms;]

Ache nasut, malakut, jabarut, lahut, char mokame chao. [There are Nasut, Malakut, Jabarut, Lahut — seek in these four stations.]

The Body as a Spiritual Vessel

According to Sufi thought, the Supreme Spirit dwells within the individual soul. Therefore, the purification of the soul is the best means of attaining Allah. The primary aspiration of the Sufi practitioner is to realise the nature of the soul. Their ideal is 'Atmanam Viddhi' — to know the self. The highest and ultimate truth of life is to attain the knowledge of Allah. Allah or the Supreme Spirit's portion is the individual soul. Therefore, to know the soul is to know the Supreme Spirit. One who has attained self-realisation has attained knowledge of Allah. In Baul thought as well, the soul is an indivisible portion of the Supreme Spirit. Bauls endeavour to know 'Who am I.' The greatest Baul master, Lalon Shah, says:

Ami ki tai janle sadhan siddha hoy, [If one knows 'who I am', spiritual sadhana finds its fulfilment;]

Ami kathar artho bhari, amate ar ami nai. [The word 'I' carries enormous meaning — within this 'I', there is no longer a separate 'I'.]

The influence of Sufism is also visible in the songs of Panju Shah: Allar nure Nabir janma, Nabir nure sara jahan. Nure jane adame tane basat kare bartaman -- From the light (Nur) of Allah, the Prophet was born; from the light of the Prophet, the whole universe. Within the light, in Adam's body, the Present One dwells. Regarding the Prophet, Nicholson has noted: He (Muhammad) is the Perfect Man in whom all the divine attributes are manifested, and a Sufi tradition ascribes to him the saying that he who has seen me has seen Allah. Thus, the manifestation of Allah and the Prophet within the human body is the Bartaman (the Present One). There is no distinction between Allah and the Prophet. This body-centred sadhana is what Bauls call Bartaman sadhana. Since ancient times, in every religious tradition, bodily purity has been given importance at the time of worship. It seems that this conception has found its culmination in body-soul philosophy (dehatmavad) and body-principle (deha-tattwa). In Sufi-influenced Baul sadhana, the body is accorded special importance. Regarding Baul sadhana, Abdul Wahab states: Renouncing the supernatural God, the soul outside the body, and the prospects of the next world, they have made themselves advocates of this-worldliness and body-centrism.

Conclusion

In both traditions, yoga-practice (yogabhyas) is an absolutely essential ritual in spiritual sadhana. In Baul songs, a blending of yoga-sadhana and Sufi sadhana-philosophy has occurred. In the sadhana of the Baul community, the practices of both the Hindu and Muslim communities have merged and become indistinguishable. The majority of Bauls are from lower Hindu castes or illiterate Muslims. The Darvesh practitioners have more of an Islamic colouring — they do not perform idol worship or worship of spirits. Their language carries much of the Islamic inflection. Therefore, the origin of the Baul tradition is indirectly connected to Sufism. Despite differences in social and religious conduct between the two traditions, there is an intimate and living connection between them. The influence of Sufism in the music, philosophy, thought, and practical lives of Lalon Fakir and the Baul-Fakirs of Bengal is deeply active.

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